

EFFICIENT GENERALIZED SIGNCRYPTION BASED ON ECC

An Braeken¹ and Pawani Porambage²

¹Industrial Engineering, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Brussel, Belgium

²Department of Communication Engineering, University of Oulu, Finland

ABSTRACT

In order to obtain promising wireless communication systems, it is necessary to maintain secure message transmissions in unicast, multicast, or broadcast scenarios. The cryptographic primitives can be incorporated when a node needs to submit messages to different receivers as encrypted and/or authenticated one-way messages. For achieving the given objective, signcryption schemes are efficient primitives.

In this paper, we first show some serious weaknesses of a previous proposed pairing-free signcryption scheme. Then, we correct the scheme and extend it to a signcryption scheme with multiple users instead of the proposed tripartite topology. The obtained signcryption scheme is further extended to a generalized signcryption scheme. All schemes consist of elliptic curve operations and satisfy also forward secrecy and public verification. To illustrate the usefulness of the generalized signcryption scheme, we show its application in the context of key management for wireless sensor networks.

KEYWORDS

Signcryption, Generalized signcryption, Elliptic Curve Discrete Logarithm Problem (ECDLP), Key management

1. INTRODUCTION

In order to obtain energy efficient message transmissions, broadcasting and multicasting communication scenarios are widely performed in wireless network settings. Due to the open air message deliveries and unreliable connection establishments, the wireless communication links are always considered to be insecure. Therefore, the key security characteristics that should be incorporated with all types of communication scenarios in wireless networks are identified as confidentiality, authentication, and integrity. The sender needs to guarantee that the message can only be read by authorized receivers (confidentiality) whereas, the receivers need to ensure about the correctness of the origin (authentication) and content of the actual message (integrity). These security requirements are efficiently achieved by a signcryption scheme.

A generalized signcryption (GSC) scheme provides either confidentiality or authentication or a combination of both. Moreover, since a GSC advocates all these security features accompanied by the possibility of sending multiple messages to different receivers in the same communication phase, a GSC scheme can be deployed in constrained wireless devices also.

The application scenarios of signcryption schemes have gone beyond the theoretical derivations to the real-time application level. In [1], an application for multi-receiver identity-based schemes has been proposed in the context of Mobile Ad hoc networks (Manets) to deal with malicious nodes. Suppose that every node has a surveillance mechanism. Then, if one node detects that its neighbor node has malicious behavior, the node sends a warning message and broadcasts this message to the whole Manet using the multi-receiver scheme. Once a node reaches a given threshold of warnings, the node is excluded from the network. Other applications are related to the key management in wireless sensor networks (WSNs) [2,3]. Signcryption is used here to share the key between the sink node and the network nodes.

In this paper, we propose the most efficient signcryption and a GSC scheme from literature, that use elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) primitives and avoid the computationally heavy bilinear operations, satisfying besides the classical security properties also forward secrecy and public verification. The signcryption scheme is an extension to multiple receivers of the tripartite signcryption scheme from [4], where we first correct a serious security problem. This scheme is then further extended to a GSC.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview about the related work. Section 3 explains the key definitions and assumptions used. In Section 4, we propose the new signcryption scheme and the extended GSC scheme. Sections 5 and 6 discuss the security and the performance aspects of the schemes respectively. We show how to apply the GSC scheme for key management of WSNs in Section 7. Finally, Section 8 concludes the paper.

2. RELATED WORK

The concept of public key signcryption was introduced by Zheng [5] in 1997. The significance of a signcryption scheme is that it simultaneously generates both encryption and signature in a single phase. Consequently, cryptographic properties such as confidentiality, integrity, authentication and non-repudiation are more efficiently obtained compared to the traditional approaches, which first encrypt and then sign the message. Since 1997, many variants of signcryption schemes with different cryptographic properties have been proposed. More particularly, the identity-based signcryption scheme was firstly introduced by Malone in 2002 [6]. In [7], Duan et. al. proposed the inclusion of multi-receiving property to the identity-based signcryption schemes. Since then, several other identity-based multi-receiving schemes were suggested in many previous literature [8].

Most of the proposed signcryption systems in literature make use of the computationally heavy operations of bilinear pairing. The first ECC based signcryption scheme was suggested in [9], which saved about 58% computational cost and about 40% communication cost compared to the signature-then-encryption approach. In [10], a recent overview is given of all the different signature schemes based on ECC that were proposed in literature. In particular, they were compared with respect to the security attributes of confidentiality, integrity, authentication, unforgeability, non-repudiation, forward secrecy, and public verification. Papers [2,3,11,12,13,14,15] were suggested to satisfy all the required security features of a signcryption scheme.

After thorough evaluation of these papers, we concluded that papers [2,12,15] have exactly the same structure. Papers [3] and [11] claim to satisfy non-repudiation and public verifiability, but

clearly do not since the private key of the receiver is required to perform the steps of the unsignryption procedure in the protocol. Reference [15] consists of a completely different approach but also requires much more ECC operations. Finally, in [13] a serious security weakness exists because the sender sends the parameter s to the receiver, where $s = tw_a$. Here w_a represents the private key of the sender and t is a parameter that can be computed by the receiver in the protocol. As a consequence, the receiver is able to derive the private key of the sender.

Another signcryption scheme from 2013 satisfying all the possible required properties, not mentioned in the review [10], can be found in [4]. However, there the number of receivers is limited to two, which is not pragmatic in real-time wireless systems. Moreover, a serious security problem exists in the key generation of the scheme.

To summarize, our proposed signcryption scheme is an extended and corrected version of the scheme from [4]. We show that this scheme is more efficient than the other existing full security-featured signcryption schemes from [2,12,15] based on basic elliptic curve (EC) operations. In addition, we extend the signcryption scheme to a generalized one by adding one extra EC multiplication at sender side.

3. SYSTEM MODEL AND ASSUMPTIONS

First, we discuss the security problem of the tripartite signcryption scheme of [4]. Then, we correct the problem and extend the scheme to a signcryption scheme with multiple receivers instead of only 2. Next, we extend this signcryption scheme to a GSC scheme with a limited additional cost.

This section explains the key definitions and the assumptions used for deriving the proposed scheme. We consider the sender S and a number of n receivers $U = \{U_1, \dots, U_n\}$, where $n \geq 2$. The identities of the sender and the receivers are respectively denoted by ID_S and ID_j with $1 \leq j \leq n$. The ECC primitives are taken from the standardized curve parameters as given in [16,17], where G is the base point generator of the curve of prime order p , defined in the finite field F_q , with q prime.

The sender's private and public keys are respectively denoted by d_S and Q_S . Each entity in the scheme has its own private-public key pair, whereas in particular, the j -th receiver's key pair is (d_j, Q_j) for $1 \leq j \leq n$. The generation of these key pairs is performed by a trusted Public Key Generator (PKG) and is explained in the next section. The node identities and the corresponding public keys are publicly known.

Operation H is a one-way cryptographic hash function (e.g., SHA2 or SHA3) that results in a number of F_q . The encryption algorithm can be considered as the well known AES or the lightweight cryptographic algorithm PRESENT. It is assumed that the given cryptographic operations and the EC parameters are identically implemented and performed at each participating entity. The original message sent by the sender is represented as M . The ciphertext C , is obtained by encrypting the message M using the key K , $C = E_K(M)$. The concatenation of two messages M_1 and M_2 is denoted by $M_1|M_2$.

For the definition of the GSC scheme, we need to introduce two assumptions, related to the hash function on the zero message and the encryption/decryption of a message under the zero-key. In particular, $H(0) = 0$ and $E_0(M) = M$, $D_0(C) = C$.

4. PROPOSED SCHEME

First, we discuss the security problem of the tripartite signcryption scheme of [4]. Then, we correct the problem and extend the scheme to a signcryption scheme with multiple receivers instead of only 2. Next, we extend this signcryption scheme to a GSC scheme with a limited additional cost.

4.1. Security problem of previous scheme

The main weakness of the scheme in [4] takes place in the key generation. The private keys for the participants are defined by the PKG, using the identity of the user and the private key of the PKG d_k . Thus, the private key of user a is derived as $d_a = d_k H(ID_a)$. Consequently, any user is able to derive the private key of the PKG. This also means that any user is able to establish own key pairs in the name of the PKG. Another serious problem is that every time a key pair of a user needs to be revoked and reset, it implies a change in either the identity of the user or the private key of the PKG and thus also all other users' key pairs.

A last issue is that the system is called an identity-based scheme. Following the definition of identity-based cryptography [18], the public key should consist of the identity of the user. Here, the identity of the user is only involved in the private key. From a security point of view, an identity-based cryptosystem guarantees the link between the public key and a given identity. In [4], this link is created by including identity-related information any time the public key of a user occurs. However, the question still remains how the valid pair, consisting of identity and public key, reaches the user. An attacker can easily mislead a user by for instance placing his public key with another identity ID_o , allowing him to read a message intended to that particular identity ID_o . An attacker could also generate its own key pair, since the particular form of the private key is not exploited in the scheme. We see two possibilities in solving this issue.

- The data containing the pairs (identity and public key of each user) is publicly published, but a third party independently checks all changes on the content.
- The most secure way would be to transmit the paired information of identity and public key by applying the signature scenario of the GSC scheme that we develop in this paper.

It needs to be mentioned that both approaches are less efficient than the key management in identity-based crypto. However, identity based crypto is typically achieved by means of bilinear operations, which we explicitly want to avoid due to their computationally heavy requirements. Since transmission costs are fundamentally smaller (order of 1000) than the computation costs of pairing operations, we will show that even with an extra communication phase of the required public key information with the signature scenario of the GSC scheme, we are still able to obtain a considerable more efficient system.

4.2. Proposed Signcryption Scheme

A signcryption scheme consists of 3 different phases. The first phase is the key generation of the private and public keys of the participants. The second part handles the signcryption, executed by

the sender. In the third phase, the receivers perform the operations individually, which is referred as the unsignryption process. We describe these different processes more into detail.

4.2.1. Key Generation

We now correctly apply the idea for the integration of the identity in the private key as in [4]. Let us also consider a PKG with (d_k, Q_k) the master private and public key pair. We also include a parameter r , which is a random value in F_q . It allows the revocation of the user's credentials and the issue of new credentials without changing the private master key or the identity of the user. The private key and public key of S and the users U_j with $1 \leq j \leq n$ is now defined as

$$\begin{aligned} d_S &= H(d_k H(ID_S | r) G) & d_j &= H(d_k H(ID_j | r) G) \\ Q_S &= d_S Q_k & Q_j &= d_j Q_k \end{aligned}$$

The private keys are securely delivered to the users of the system in off-line mode. The master public key Q_k is stored in all nodes. The tuple $(ID_i, Q_i, H(ID_i | Q_i))$ is made publicly available for all users U_i in the system. The last element in this tuple is to ensure the link between the identity and the public key.

4.2.2. Signryption

This process consists of 6 steps. Denote by $M=(M_1|...|M_n)$ the message to be encrypted for the corresponding users of the system $U=(U_1, ..., U_n)$ where each M_j is intended for user U_j with $1 \leq j \leq n$. We want to note that the multi-receiver property, exactly one message to all receivers, can also be easily included in the algorithm by integrating the key derivation of [19] after step 3 of the signryption and step 5 of the unsignryption procedure.

In order to start the signryption process, the identities and the corresponding public keys of the receivers $(Q_1, ..., Q_n)$ are queried by the sender. Let us here assume that these values are securely stored in a public environment (cf. first approach). The following steps are then performed by the sender.

1. The sender chooses a random parameter r_1 and computes $k_S = r_1 Q_k$.
2. For all users U_j , with $1 \leq j \leq n$, the parameter k_j is computed as $k_j = H(r_1 H(ID_j) Q_j)$.
3. The ciphertext is computed, $C_j = E_{k_j}(M_j)$. Denote by $C=(C_1|...|C_n)$.
4. Then, the hash h is calculated as $h = H(k_S | C | ID_S | U)$.
5. Finally, we compute $s = r_1 - h d_S$.
6. The message to transmit, consists now of $s | h | C | ID_S | U$.

4.2.3. Unsignryption

Any individual receiver U_j , with $1 \leq j \leq n$ can now execute the following process.

A preliminary step before the unsignryption can start, is to request or query the corresponding public key Q_S of ID_S and to check its integrity by means of the hash $H(ID_S | Q_S)$. Then, all required info is available to check the signature and decrypt the message of the transmitted data $s | h | C | ID_S | U$.

1. The intermediate point $P = s Q_k + h Q_S$ is first computed.
2. Now, the value $k_S = P$.
3. In the next step, we can compute $h' = H(k_S | C | ID_S | U)$.

4. If $h'=h$, the message origin and validity is verified and we can continue the process.
Otherwise, we stop.
5. Finally, the value $k_j=H(d_jH(ID_j)P)$ can be computed.
6. Thus, the decryption leads to $M_j=D_{k_j}(C_j)$.

The different steps in this signcryption protocol are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Proposed signcryption scheme.

Signcryption	Unsigncryption
1. Choose $r_1, k_S = r_1Q_k$	1. $P = sQ_k + hQ_S$
2. For all $j, k_j = H(r_1H(ID_j)Q_k)$	2. $k_S = P$
3. For all $j, C_j = E_{k_j}(M_j) \rightarrow C = (C_1 \dots C_n)$	3. $h' = H(k_S(C ID_S U))$
4. $h = H(k_S(C ID_S U))$	4. $h' = h?$
5. $s = r_1 - hd_S$	5. $k_j = H(d_jH(ID_j)P)$
6. Send $s h C ID_S U$	6. $M_j = D_{k_j}(C_j)$

4.3. Generalized Signcryption Scheme

There are 3 main scenarios in a GSC scheme.

- Signcryption scenario: sender and receivers are determined and the message is encrypted and provided with a signature.
- Signature scenario: Only the sender is determined. The message is only provided with a signature and no encryption is performed.
- Encryption scenario: Only the receivers are determined. The message is encrypted and signed by an anonymous sender.

We now show how the scheme from the previous paragraph with some small adaptations can be transformed to a GSC scheme. The main trick we use is to add an extra random value r_2 for which the corresponding EC point $R_2 = r_2Q_k$ is calculated. This point R_2 is also included in the transmitted message. As a consequence, R_2 can be used as a kind of temporary public key and r_2 as the corresponding temporary private key of the sender. Thanks to the integration of this pair (r_2, R_2) , the encryption scenario of the GSC scheme, where the sender is unknown, can be defined.

The key generation is the same as described above. The input parameters of the GSC scheme are determined by $(ID_S, d_S, Q_S, U_1, d_1, Q_1, \dots, U_n, d_n, Q_n)$. We now describe the different modes.

4.3.1. Signcryption Scenario

The input of the system in signcryption scenario consists of $(ID_S, d_S, Q_S, U_1, d_1, Q_1, \dots, U_n, d_n, Q_n)$. The protocol is very similar as the signcryption protocol from the previous paragraph. The main differences are

- The introduction of R_2 (step 2 in signcryption mode) as replacement of Q_S (step 1 in unsigncryption mode).

- Replacement of d_s by r_2 in the computation of the signature (step 6 in signcryption mode).
- The additional transmission of R_2 in the message and the corresponding inclusion into the input of the hash to ensure integrity of the transmitted message.

The different steps are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. GSC Signcryption Scenario.

Signcryption	Unsigncryption
1. Choose r_1 , $k_S = r_1 Q_k$	1. $P = sQ_k + hR_2$
2. Choose r_2 , $R_2 = r_2 Q_k$	2. $k_S = P$
3. For all j , $k_j = H(r_1 H(ID_j) Q_j)$	3. $h' = H(k_S C ID_S R_2 U)$
4. For all j , $C_j = E_{k_j}(M_j) \rightarrow C = (C_1 \dots C_n)$	4. $h' = h?$
5. $h = H(k_S C ID_S R_2 U)$	5. $k_j = H(d_j H(ID_j) P)$
6. $s = r_1 - hr_2$	6. $M_j = D_{k_j}(C_j)$
7. Send $s h R_2 C ID_S U$	

4.3.2. Signature Scenario

The input of the system in the signature scenario consists of $(ID_S, d_S, Q_S, 0, \dots, 0)$, since the receivers are unknown. Here we use the assumptions that $E_0(M) = M$, $D_0(C) = C$ and $H(0) = 0$. Consequently, steps 3 and 4 from the signcryption mode and steps 5 and 6 from the unsigncryption mode, are drastically simplified in the signature scenario.

The different steps are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. GSC Signature Scenario.

Signcryption	Unsigncryption
1. Choose r_1 , $k_S = r_1 Q_k$	1. $P = sQ_k + hR_2$
2. Choose r_2 , $R_2 = r_2 Q_k$	2. $k_S = P$
3. For all j , $k_j = H(0) = 0$	3. $h' = H(k_S C ID_S R_2 0)$
4. For all j , $C_j = E_0(M_j) = M_j \rightarrow C = (M_1 \dots M_n)$	4. $h' = h?$
5. $h = H(k_S C ID_S R_2 0)$	5. $k_j = 0$
6. $s = r_1 - hr_2$	6. $M_j = D_0(C_j)$
7. Send $s h R_2 C ID_S 0$	

4.3.3. Encryption Scenario

The input of the system in the encryption scenario consists of $(0, 0, 0, U_1, d_1, Q_1, \dots, U_n, d_n, Q_n)$, since the sender is unknown. Due to the introduction of the pair (r_2, R_2) that takes over the role of the sender's key pair (d_s, Q_s) , the encryption scenario consists of the same operations as the signcryption scenario. The different steps are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. GSC Encryption Scenario.

Signcryption	Unsigncryption
1. Choose r_1 , $k_S = r_1Q_k$	1. $P = sQ_k + hR_2$
2. Choose r_2 , $R_2 = r_2Q_k$	2. $k_S = P$
3. For all j , $k_j = H(r_1H(ID_j)Q_j)$	3. $h' = H(k_S C 0 R_2 U)$
4. For all j , $C_j = E_{k_j}(M_j) \rightarrow C = (C_1 ... C_n)$	4. $h' = h?$
5. $h = H(k_S C 0 R_2 U)$	5. $k_j = H(d_jH(ID_j)P)$
6. $s = r_1 - hr_2$	6. $M_j = D_{k_j}(C_j)$
7. Send $s h R_2 C 0 U$	

To conclude, with an extra cost of one point multiplication (cf. step 2 at sender side in the scheme) and the transmission of one extra ECC point, a GSC scheme is obtained from the signcryption scheme. Moreover, it should be noticed that thanks to the introduction of an extra random value r_2 , the private key of the sender is better protected. In [20], it is considered as a weakness to make the private key dependent of only one random value. This is also the case in the first proposed signcryption scheme, where $s = r_1 - hd_S$ and s, h are part of the transmitted message.

5. SECURITY ANALYSIS

In the previous section, we proposed 2 schemes, a signature scheme and a GSC scheme as extension of this signature scheme. The extension of the signature scheme to the GSC scheme consists of the inclusion of an extra tuple $(r_2, R_2 = r_2Q_k)$, that takes over the role of a temporary private and public key pair. The parameter R_2 is on the one hand included in the transmitted message. On the other hand, at the place where an operation was involved with the private key of the sender (step 6 of signcryption procedure), the parameter r_2 is used. Consequently, due to the Elliptic Curve Discrete Logarithm Problem (ECDLP), the security of the GSC scheme is completely determined by the security of the signcryption scheme. Therefore, we can here restrict our discussion to the security of our first proposed signcryption scheme. Let us start with showing the correctness of the protocol. Next, we shortly discuss the most important security properties of the scheme.

5.1. Correctness of the protocol

There are 2 checks to be made. One check is related with the verification of the hash and the other with the derivation of the EC point. Both are based on the same principle.

5.1.1. Verification of the Hash

We need to check if the determination of k_S by sender and receiver corresponds to each other. Let us start from the side of the receiver and show that we obtain the same calculation as the

$$\begin{aligned} k_S &= P = sQ_k + hQ_S \\ &= (r_1 - hd_S)Q_k + hd_SQ_k = r_1Q_k \end{aligned}$$

5.1.2. Derivation of Point on EC

Again sender and receiver have a different calculation for the computation of the shared secret key k_j . Starting from the receiver leads to the following result:

$$\begin{aligned} k_j &= H(d_j H(ID_j) P) = H(d_j H(ID_j) (s Q_k + h Q_s)) \\ &= H(H(ID_j) ((r_1 - h d_s) d_j Q_k + h d_j d_s Q_k)) \\ &= H(H(ID_j) r_1 Q_j) \end{aligned}$$

5.2. Other Security Properties

The security of the whole scheme is based on the ECDLP. It is exploited two times, first to derive a common shared EC point and second for ensuring authentication and integrity of the message. Let us now shortly describe the different security properties of the protocol. Again, for the same reason as explained above, we focus on the base signcryption scheme.

5.2.1. Public Verifiability and Non-repudiation

Thanks to the particular construction of the private and public keys of the entities, a public verifiable scheme is created. This means that any third party without knowledge of the private key of sender or receiver(s) can validate the signcrypted message. Since anyone with knowledge of the master public key Q_k in the scheme can execute the computations as shown in the derivation of k_s above. Then, anyone can also check the value of the hash h . As a consequence, also non-repudiation, allowing any third party to validate the origin of the message, is obtained in the scheme.

5.2.2. Unforgeability

The scheme is also unforgeable, which means that only the intended sender can produce a valid message-signature pair. No other entity can send a message $s|h|C|ID_S|U$, since the values s , h and C are either directly or indirectly linked with the given identity ID_S or the private key d_S of the sender S . First of all, with respect to the public verifiable part of the protocol, being the check of the parameter h , it is not possible due to the ECDLP for deriving the random value r_1 in the computation of a correct value for s . Secondly, also a valid value for the secret key k_j is impossible to construct without knowledge of the private key of the sender due to the ECDLP.

The random value r_1 is generated in the beginning of the protocol. This value is integrated in all the steps of the protocol where the identity or private key of the sender is involved. The first step is in the computation of the EC point shared with the receivers. The second step is related to the derivation of the parameter k_s , which leads to the first validity check at the side of the receiver. As a consequence, no replay attacks can be performed in order to forge a signature.

5.2.3. Message Integrity

It is clear that the message integrity is obtained thanks to the hash h , transmitted in the message. This hash value includes information of the ciphertext C , the values k_s , ID_S and U . The value k_s depends on the random value r_1 and cannot be replayed.

5.2.4. Authentication

In the signcryption scheme the authentication of the identities of sender and receivers are obtained thanks to 2 measurements. First, the key pairs, generated by the PKG, are based on the identities of sender and receiver. This follows from the fact that the private keys, incorporating the identities, of the involved entities are used. Also at the moment the public key is used from an entity, the corresponding identity is included in the operation, which creates a dependency between the public key and the identity as is the case in identity-based cryptography. We assumed that alternations to the list $(ID_b, Q_b, H(ID_i | Q_i))$ are independently verified by a third party.

5.2.5. Forward Secrecy

Even if the private key of the sender is revealed, an attacker is not able to derive the secret key k_j for the decryption of messages, sent in the past. This key k_j is constructed using a random value r_j , which is deleted in the sender's memory after sending the message. The value r_j cannot be derived from k_s , due to the ECDLP.

6. EFFICIENCY

It is fair to compare our scheme with other systems in literature that achieve the same (i.e. all required) security attributes and also restrict to basic EC operations. In any case, these systems are much more efficient than the ones that include the computationally heavy pairing operation. As mentioned in [21], for binary fields, pairing operations behave almost 5 times worse than EC point multiplications operations in timing and energy performance. For prime fields, the difference increases to a factor of 16. Consequently, one pairing operation has a huge impact in a signcryption protocol, taken into account that our signcryption scheme with one receiver only requires two point multiplications from sender's side.

As follows from the review paper [10] and our analysis afterwards as explained in Section 2, only the schemes from [2,12,15] can be used for comparison. The schemes from these three papers turn out to all have exactly the same structure.

Moreover, applying the same trick of including an extra random value r_2 and a corresponding EC point R_2 , makes it possible to extend their signcryption scheme also to a GSC scheme.

Table 5 compares the most computationally heavy operations between our signcryption scheme and the ones of [2,12,15]. These operations include the EC point multiplications (PM) and point additions (PA). We also compare the number of operations for the corresponding GSC schemes, taking into account that the scheme of [2,12,15] is extended the same way as proposed in this paper.

Table 5. Comparison of EC operations with n the number of receivers.

	Sign PM	Sign PA	Unsign PM	Unsign PA
[2,12,15]	$n+2$	0	3	1
Our Signcryption Scheme	$n+1$	0	3	1
GSC for [2,12,15]	$n+3$	0	3	1
Our GSC	$n+2$	0	3	1

As can be concluded from Table 5, our signcryption scheme requires one PM less at sender side than the scheme of [2,12,15]. In addition, an inverse field operation is required in the schemes [2,12,15] to compute the signature parameter s , while we only need a subtraction. The same difference is consequently translated into the corresponding GSC schemes, where only 1 extra PM operation is required at the sender's side. Consequently, for 1 receiver, our signcryption scheme outperforms the other existing ones with 33% and our GSC scheme with 25%.

When we want to apply the second proposed approach, being the application of the signature scenario of the GSC scheme, for delivering the pairs identity and public keys of the receivers to the sender, we have to add 2 extra PM and 1 PA. As shown in [21], one pairing operation requires around five times more energy consumption than one PM. Consequently, our scheme is able to offer the same security objectives than an identity-based signcryption scheme and will always be more efficient than these identity-based proposals.

7. APPLICATION IN KEY MANAGEMENT

We now shortly discuss the applicability of our GSC scheme for the key management of WSNs. Let us assume that there is a PKG that generates the private and public keys following the method explained in Section 4 and distributes the private keys in off-line mode to the different nodes of the network.

There is one powerful base node (BN) that decides the cluster formation, based on the energy level and the location. The identity and public key of the BN is also stored at each node. The BN contains a list of sensor node identities and corresponding public keys. The following steps are then performed in the network to manage the key distribution among the nodes.

1. The BN broadcasts an info update request to all nodes in the network. This message only needs a valid signature from the BN.
2. Each individual node sends its info to the BN, using the signcryption scenario.
3. Based on that information, the BN calculates the candidate cluster heads. For each cluster, the list, containing the members of each cluster and their corresponding cluster head, is sent to all nodes in that cluster. Note that in order to completely determine an entity in the network, the identity should be accompanied with the corresponding public key. This message is only signed.
4. The BN signcrypts a secret shared key for each of the cluster heads.
5. The cluster heads signcrypt a secret group key for the whole cluster. Note that this corresponds with the multi-receiver signcryption scheme. The nodes first verify if the identity of the sender corresponds with one of the nodes contained in the previous message.
6. Suppose that every node contains a surveillance mechanism, as considered in [1]. The node can then detect malicious behavior of its neighbor nodes and send this information in encrypted mode to the BN.

Table 6 summarizes the number of computationally heavy operations, PM and PA, corresponding to each step, executed by the BN, cluster nodes, and the remaining sensor nodes. Let m denote the number of different clusters and t the number of warning messages sent from the nodes of the

International Journal on Cryptography and Information Security (IJCIS), Vol. 5, No. 2, June 2015
network to the BN. The total number of operations in the table corresponds with the total executed from step 1 till 5, i.e. the key management of one single phase.

Table 6. Number of PM and PA in key management protocol using our GSC.

Step	BN	Cluster node	Sensor node
1	$2PM$	$2PM+1PA$	$2PM+1PA$.
2	$3PM+1PA$	$3PM$	$3PM$
3	$m(2PM)$	$2PM+1PA$	$2PM+1PA$
4	$m(3PM)$	$3PM+1PA$	0
5	0	$3PM$	$3PM+1PA$
6	$3PM+1PA$	$t(3PM)$	$t(3PM)$
Total	$(5+5m)PM+PA$	$13PM + PA$	$10PM+3PA$.

8. CONCLUSIONS

A very efficient signcryption scheme that satisfies all the required security features, based on the basic EC operations, is presented in this paper. A simple trick is proposed to extend the signcryption scheme to a generalized version with a very small additional cost of one extra PM at sender side. Both schemes are shown to be more efficient than the others in literature. As application of the GSC scheme, we illustrate the key management in WSNs using this protocol.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the TETRA grant of the Flanders agency for Innovation by Science and Technology, and the Short Term Scientific Mission performed under COST Action IC1303.

REFERENCES

- [1] Wu, L., An ID-Based Multi-Receiver Signcryption Scheme In MANET, Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology, Vol. 46, No. 1, 2012
- [2]]Esam A. A. A.H., Doaa E.S, Hazem H. A., A New Forward Secure Elliptic Curve Signcryption Key Management (FS-ECSKM) Scheme for Heterogeneous Wireless Sensor Networks, International Journal of Computer Science and Technology, Vol. 2, No 2, pp 19-23, 2011
- [3] Bala S., Sharma G. and Verma A.K., An Improved Forward Secure Elliptic Curve Signcryption Key Management Scheme for Wireless Sensor Networks, Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering (Springer Link), Vol. 215, 2013
- [4] Elkamchouchi H.M., Elkheir E.F.E. and Abouelseoud Y., A pairing-free identity based tripartite signcryption scheme, International Journal on Cryptography and Information Security (IJCIS), Vol. 3, No. 4, 2013
- [5] Zheng Y., Digital Signcryption or How to Achieve Cost(Signature and Encryption) \ll Cost (Signature)+Cost(Encryption), LNCS Advances in Cryptology-CRYPTO97, Springer-Verlag Press, 1997, pp. 165-179
- [6] Malone-Lee J, Identity based signcryption, Cryptology ePrintArchive, 2002 <http://eprint.iacr.org/2002/098.pdf>
- [7] Duan S., and Zhenfu C., Efficient and provably secure multi-receiver identity-based signcryption, Information Security and Privacy, pp. 195-206, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2006
- [8] List of papers around signcryption (1007-2007), <http://www.signcryption.org/publications/>

International Journal on Cryptography and Information Security (IJCIS), Vol. 5, No. 2, June 2015

- [9] Zheng Y., Imai H., How to construct efficient signcryption schemes on elliptic curves, Information Processing Letters, Vol. 68, No.5, pp. 227 - 233, 1998
- [10] Singh A.K., A Review of Elliptic Curve based Signcryption Schemes, International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 102, No. 6, 2014
- [11] Amounas F., Sadki H., El Kinani E.H., An Efficient Signcryption Scheme based on The Elliptic Curve Discrete Logarithm Problem, International Journal of Information and Network Security, Vol. 2 No. 3, pp. 253-259, 2013
- [12] Mohamed E., Elkamchouchi H., Elliptic Curve Signcryption with Encrypted Message Authentication and Forward Secrecy, International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security, Vol.9, No.1, pp 395-398, 2009
- [13] Toorani M., Shirazi A.A.B., An elliptic curve-based signcryption scheme with forward secrecy, Journal of Applied Sciences, Vol. 9, No.6, pp. 1025 -1035, 2010
- [14] Ahirwal R., Jain A., Jain Y. K., Signcryption Scheme that Utilizes Elliptic Curve for both Encryption and Signature Generation, International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 62, No. 9, pp. 41-48, 2013
- [15] Das S., Samal B., An Elliptic Curve based Signcryption Protocol using Java, International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 66, No. 4, pp. 44-49, 2013
- [16] SEC 2: Recommended Elliptic Curve Domain Parameters, Certicom Research, Standards for Efficient Cryptography Version 1.0, September 2000. [Online]. Available: <http://www.secg.org/collateral/sec2final.pdf>
- [17] Recommended Elliptic Curves for Federal Government Use, National Institute of Standards and Technology, August 1999. [Online]. Available: <http://csrc.nist.gov/groups/ST/toolkit/documents/dss/NISTReCur.pdf>
- [18] Shamir A., Identity-Based Cryptosystems and Signature Schemes, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Vol. 196, pp 47-53, 1985
- [19] Qin. H., Dai Y., Wang Z., Identity-based multi-receiver threshold signcryption scheme, Security and Communication Networks, Vol. 4, No. 11, pp 1331-1337, 2011
- [20] Mohsen Toorani and Ali Asghar Beheshti Shirazi, Cryptanalysis of an efficient signcryption scheme with forward secrecy based on elliptic curve, In Proceedings of International Conference on Computer and Electrical Engineering (ICCEE'08), pp. 428-432.
- [21] Piotr Szczechowiak, Leonardo B. Oliveira , Michael Scott, Martin Collier, and Ricardo Dahab, NanoECC: Testing the Limits of Elliptic Curve Cryptography in Sensor Networks, European conference on Wireless Sensor Networks (EWSN)

Authors

An Braeken obtained her MSc Degree in Mathematics from the University of Gent in 2002. In 2006, she received her PhD in engineering sciences from the KULeuven at the research group COSIC (Computer Security and Industrial Cryptography). In 2007, she became professor at Erasmushogeschool Brussel (currently since 2013, VUB) in the Industrial Sciences Department. Prior to joining the Erasmushogeschool Brussel, she worked for almost 2 years at a management consulting company BCG. Her current interests include cryptography, security protocols for sensor networks, secure and private localization techniques, and FPGA implementations.

Pawani Porambage is currently a PhD student in Department of Communications Engineering at University of Oulu, Finland. She obtained her Bachelor Degree in Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering in 2010 from University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka and her Master's Degree in Ubiquitous Networking and Computer Networking in 2012 from University of Nice Sophia-Anipolis, France. Her main research interests include lightweight security protocols, security and privacy on Internet of Things, and Wireless Sensor Networks.

